

Role of a Teacher vis-à-vis Learners' heterogeneity and Prescriptivism of syllabus: Some Critical Observations on ELT classrooms in Rural India

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Abstract: *An ELT classroom in rural India always bids the educators address the issue of learners' heterogeneity. Unfortunately, a common syllabus is prescribed to all with a compromised assumption that the whole class has had the same background knowledge and uniform existing proficiency level. But beside the heterogeneous factors mentioned, the learners themselves often have different agenda, making the task of a teacher even more complicated. The best solution on the part of a teacher in this context would be first to identify efficiency-based or background-based groups, and then to deal with them accordingly. Prioritizing the learners' skills in listening and reading, the present article analyses the classroom challenges to be posed potentially by student heterogeneity and prescriptivism of the curriculum. The discussion ends with some fresh lights on the prospective measures (to go beyond prescriptive syllabus) that can be adopted in such L₂ classrooms to make pedagogy even more effective.*

Keywords: *Heterogeneous classroom, syllabus, ELT, learners' proficiency, Listening, Reading, L₂ acquisition, teacher's role.*

1. Introduction

An Indian ELT class is generally characterized by students' heterogeneity in terms of background and existing proficiency level (in addition to intelligence factors). For an effective teaching-learning classroom environment and substantial L₂ acquisition, in an ELT classroom in rural India the first and foremost requirement is to address the issue of learners' heterogeneity. Unfortunately, a single syllabus is prescribed to all the students with a compromised assumption that the whole class has had the same background knowledge and uniform existing proficiency level. It's only the teacher who is assigned the responsibility to make the best out of the learners as well as the syllabus. Thus, the inherent problems relating to them in an Indian ELT classroom are (1) heterogeneous groups of learners and (2) prescriptivism of syllabus. A rural Indian ELT class is invariably is characterized by its diversity of its learners, their heterogeneous family backgrounds from linguistic point of view. Especially in the rural schools, few students have a family background with some practices of English at home by the parents or other family members. But majority is the class is from families where nobody uses English. It should be kept in mind by the teacher, and do something for the back-loggers.

The basic objective in pedagogy is to ensure that the learners are uniformly exposed to the challenges of learning tasks, have equal access to resources, and have equal-status participation in classroom activities. Teacher must make his classroom a site where learners are engaged in intellectual rigours and linguistic richness of pedagogy.

2. Literature Review

Curriculum and syllabus¹ are not synonymous at all. As a subpart of curriculum, syllabus specifies the units and course content, i.e. what is to be taught, learnt and tested (Allen 1984, Prabhu 1987, Richards 2001). These thinkers deemed syllabus to be more prescriptive. But, considering syllabus as the teacher's statement or definition of contents and objectives, Brumfit (1984) and Yalden (1987) think, a good syllabus leads to the sequences of learning, a dual progression of linear and spiral learning. Nunan's (1988) take on syllabus is: "(it is)...a framework within

which activities can be carried out: a teaching device to facilitate learning.” Breen (1987) follows the traditional path in defining syllabus, it is “the meeting point of a perspective upon language itself, upon using language, and upon teaching and learning” (83).

ELT critics and thinkers discussed much about the teachers’ role and duty in connecting the learners to the primary objectives of the curriculum through the ‘prescribed’ syllabus. Critics like Valdés (2001), Bartolome (2021) and others pointed out the necessary conditions for the proper development of academic discourse in a heterogeneous classroom². While their discussions are concerned with the linguistic heterogeneity, Gardner (1995) or Sternberg (1998) have suggested ways for the teachers to treat the issue of diversified abilities, multiple intelligence or varying intellectual faculties among the students. The most effective way of handling this heterogeneity/student diversity is to divide the learners into sub-groups according to their respective talent, intelligence or ability and to form productive group tasks (Cohen 1994, Lotan 1997, Sulman 1998). Fradd and Okhee (1999) and Carrasquillo et.al. (1995) put more emphasis much more on teachers’ role here than on the syllabus itself, since teachers can address these complicated issues by developing learner-centric oral and written academic discourses even going beyond the periphery of the syllabus but in consonance with the primary objectives of the curriculum.

3. Problems in Indian ELT classrooms

As per the commoners’ experiences in India, it may be claimed that an English language teacher has to play multiple roles at a time. A teacher is always a learner. Besides, the English teacher has to be a facilitator, assessor, evaluator and manager. Teacher is probably the most significant point in the learner-teacher-syllabus triangle. Students always come from different backgrounds with different obstacles, different levels of language proficiency³ and needs. Furthermore, the curriculum or the syllabus itself is often rigorously prescriptive, making the task of a teacher even harder. The English teacher should understand all these, and identify the areas the focus should be on. As very little can be done to the syllabus or curriculum, at the very beginning, the teacher should develop a positive attitude to the learning process in the students. To do it, he should provide proper meaning contexts in which students would practice the English language.

What are the major challenges in an English classroom in India at the intermediate level? Learners in an Indian ELT classroom have different agenda that are formulated by their idiosyncratic desires or respective backgrounds. How do their orientations / plans impact teaching? For the beginners, the primary agendum that the English language learners bring to the classroom is that they must have better proficiency in English to be more eligible for the job market. The proficiency in English communication coupled with the fluency in Spoken English skill is held to be the most desired professional qualification. Another agendum observed in the English language classroom is the social prestige associated with the knowledge of the language, too often misjudged through the spoken English fluency.

But the English learners, who completed the preliminary level of study and have been through to the advanced-level, have a different set of agenda. They have a dream to speak English as a foreign speaker, as they find on TV. They desire to interact freely and fluently with the native English speakers with improved confidence. In doing so, they need to identify their probable weaknesses and overcome them. English skills are expected to yield academic/professional benefits, like an

extra edge at the interview or big exams in the national/international level. Advanced learners are also interested in making their linguistic skills more profitable in their commercial/business activities. All these expectations, learners' orientation or future plans guided to a great extent the way the privately-run English training institutes run their courses. It happened so, since the success of these training courses depend a lot on the fulfillment of the aspirants' professional/academic goals and attainments.

4. Going beyond the ELT Syllabus: Problems and prospects

If the syllabus is defined as a teacher's statement, leading to a dual progression of linear and spiral learning, as Brumfit (1984) and Yalden (1987) suggest, then the teacher is supposed to have a lot more liberty to conduct his classes applying his own imagination and innovative ideas. Nunan (1988) also considered syllabus as a liberal tool to promote activities in the classrooms that can facilitate learning.

We can make a list of some aspects of language teaching that do not directly find entry in the current ELT syllabus in India, but the teacher has to incorporate in the classroom. The following are the innovative aspects of language teaching that a teacher may incorporate in the classroom:

- To devise ways and tasks to address MI or diverse intelligence of the learners in the classroom;
- To somehow expose the learners to the real L₂ context, may be through exposure to English newspaper, audio-visual news on TV, films or sports commentary;
- To assign role play and to promote performing arts in English;
- To encourage and motivate to use of English on campus, e.g. in conducting school programmes, or by introducing daily news casting sessions in English on rotation basis;
- To encourage and design language games in the classroom for the learners;
- To introduce peer teaching by the learners, e.g. senior student teaching the junior class in English;
- To publish English wall magazine where students must contribute;
- To supply of newspapers, magazines and story books for regular perusal by the learners;
- To hold special remedial classes for the back-loggers. Though it goes against the idea of 'heterogeneous grouping'⁴, such special classes can help the needed to have the desired progress.

These are some of the aspects of English language learning not covered by the syllabus but to be incorporated by the teacher. If implemented, they will surely improve the learning environment.

5. Teachers' Role in Teaching a Text: Simplification

In India a big chunk of the English language syllabus is devoted to the literary texts and acquisition of the language skills through literature. But a big problem in the ELT classroom here is the student's apathy to or lack of proper understanding of the literary texts. Here a teacher can resort to the process called adaptation and simplification. In order to make a relatively complicated text (e.g. a classic or a masterpiece of stalwarts like Shakespeare/Dickens) reach out to a wider audience, some simplification or adaptation is often done. Such simplification may involve

- i) **information control:** It refers to the simplification of the whole content

through making a summary, avoiding secondary or tertiary details about the characters, setting or even some of the events. Taking up the primary storyline of the original, it may even take the form of a re-writing of the whole text in accordance with the linguistic proficiency of the target readers.

- ii) **lexical control:** It means the replacement of the complicated words or phrases (presumably unsuitable for the target group of readers) with the easier equivalents. Too much rhetorical/symbolical words, typical technical terms, jargons, slangs culture-specific terms, dialectic items are generally avoided in the simplified version. Sometimes, instead of any replacement, the lexical items may be altogether removed.
- iii) **structural control:** This kind of control mechanism refers to the use of short and simple sentences/expressions instead of long and bombastic constructions, either complex or compound. Periphrastic expressions or sentences characterized as Johnsonese style of expressions are put aside in favour of some direct and simple expressions. The sentence like “It was the humblest human habitation that got devoured right at the instant by a huge flame of conflagration” may be replaced with “A big fire burnt the slum down in no time”.

When all these controls are put into force, unfortunately the real author became truly very hard to identify, because a proper simplification through these mechanisms call for a second authorship.

The question still remains: Can these processes help the reader in better comprehension of a text?

If we take the word ‘text’ in its true critical sense (so much talked about by I.A. Richards, Barthes, Foucault and Derrida), the answer is: ‘No, not at all.’ Alterations and substitution that the simplification processes involve may subvert the essential reality, but cannot help readers understand the ‘text’ any better.

On the other hand, if one takes the word ‘text’ in the sense of ‘the work itself’, then the answer would be ‘No, not exactly’. The original text (=the work) is a work prior to the simplification processes applied; the one after simplification has become a different text (=work). If any similarity is there between the pre- and post-simplification versions, it is the primary story-line, set of characters and events. But these elements only cannot make any piece of composition a complete work of art/literature. There are style, message, discourse, plot-construction, structural design, use of the language and many other things. All these together make some composition a true work, a text. As such, only by summarizing, simplifying the words/phrases or sentences, readers can be helped out in following the story-line better, nothing else. Rather, these processes run the risk of diverting the readers away from the true beauty of a ‘text’.

5.1 Dipping Deeper into the ELT Syllabus: Teaching Poetry

To teaching poetry is probably the most challenging task for a teacher, since true poetry cannot be taught unless and until it is felt. Still, as a text is prescribed in the language classroom primarily in order to teach the linguistic skills, we would pay more attention to the linguistic devices that technically make poems different from prose. First, let us take up, for an example, the poem “Virtue” by George Herbert (See Appendix-I(A) for the full Text), and explain what are the linguistic devices the learners’ attention can be drawn to:

- **Relations between parts of a text through lexical cohesive devices:** In this poem, a strong lexical cohesion exists among the words ‘day’, ‘rose’, and ‘spring’; for they are interrelated through their shared attributes of quality,

beauty, and transience. Another instance of lexical cohesion is found in the repetition of the phrase ‘must die’, which recurs at the end of each of the poem’s first three stanzas. In every stanza, a consistent use of words denoting death or decay is observable—such as ‘fall’, ‘grave’, ‘close’, and ‘turn to coal’. By the end of the fourth stanza, cohesion is established through the introduction of a contrasting sentiment, conveyed by the phrase ‘chiefly lives’. Thus, it becomes evident how these words collectively embody a lexical relationship, established through a continuity of lexical meaning.

- **Relations between parts of a text through grammatical cohesive devices:** There comes into play the grammatical cohesion through the employment of compound sentence structures in each of the poem’s four stanzas; in this context, the words ‘For’, ‘And’, ‘And’, and ‘But’ serve as conjunctions.
- **Indicators in discourse :** In the very first line of the poem, the emphatic adverb ‘so’ functions as a cohesive element through its prominent usage. The repetition of the word ‘And’ signals a linear or sequential progression within the discourse; conversely, the word ‘but’—positioned at the very end—signifies a sharp or distinct contrast.

Now, let us take up the next example, another poem, i.e. “The Song of the Whale” of Kit Wright (See Appendix-I(B) for the full Text) to understand the questions like:

- (a) What language skills may be potentially developed through this poem?
- (b) What problems might the teacher encounter in teaching this poem?

It was previously believed that poetry is something that is remote from the contexts of language teaching. But as many surveys has proved that, this poem as a learning material is as good as any other language teaching content, rather complementary to the other materials. It teaches those skills that other materials often neglect. When in the classroom (or elsewhere), the students recite, read or listen to poetry, it definitely increases their knowledge of vocabulary, the words and phrases, their rhetorical connotations, of sentence structures, collocation and other syntactical rules, rhythmical and rhyming effects/devices and also the creative skills. Along with the training in the four basic linguistic skills (LSRW i.e. listening, speaking, reading and writing), the poem also helps student to gather some communication skills too. Like any other short lyric poems, it also teaches as to how thoughts and emotions can be draped in a beautiful imaginative/emotive language.

In ELT classrooms, teaching/learning poetry is always challenging. Though poetry is basically a personal experience, “The Song of the Whale” has a unique universal appeal. It eloquently appeals to our conscience for not killing the whales for our own benefits. The message is very serious and it would be very challenging to teach the students this disturbing aspect of human cruelty. The teacher might face the problem of encouraging the students’ emotional responses to the poem. To enjoy the poem, all the learners need to have much attention and concentration; they must apply simultaneously their head and heart. But some students may feel bored in reading the poem. Actually, the heterogeneity in the class cannot be ignored, and it may be a problem in the class, as poetry is not for everyone. Both the teacher and students should have extra emotional and intellectual efforts to make a true sense of the piece. Besides, students might be in trouble in learning the linguistic aspects, activities, since solving grammatical problems, soon after the emotional exercise would be hard to adapt to.

As regards the classroom activities of the teacher and the proceedings may be like the following:

Pre-Reading Activities:

- Will ask them who love poems and recitation
- Will give some idea about poetry and verse, the poet Herbert.
- Will draw attention to title of the poem and its meaning
- Will ask the students what they think may be the greatest virtue in our life
- Will share with them Herbert's reply to the question.

While-Reading Activities:

- Will read out (rather recite) the whole poem;
- Will write on the board the difficult words and their meaning (as and when encountered)
- Will explain the images 'rose' 'spring' etc.
- Will ask the students for their feelings about these.
- Will invite the students for recitation of the poem

Post- Reading Activities:

- Will ask simple questions based on the text after reading session I.
- Will give the students a task of summarizing the poem in their own words.
- Will ask if the title is appropriate? And why?
- Will ask if they agree with Herbert's view. Their opinions would be invited.

6. Going beyond the 'Prescribed' Syllabus

The teacher can make his classroom activities more effective if he/she deviates productively with different language activities. Thereby, the possible monopoly of the syllabus can be challenged with a great positive result. The point is that going beyond the syllabus does not necessarily mean to go astray and fail the main objectives of the curriculum. Here the term, 'productive digression' or 'creative deviation' can make the maximum out of it.

6.1 ELT class and 'Productive Digression': Simulation and Role Play

By 'productive digression' it meant that the teacher can teach a module in the syllabus like a play (or its extract/abridged version) but with his own innovative techniques that are a bit unusual and not prescribed formally by the syllabus design or curricular framework. The techniques like 'simulation' and 'role play' can be much effectively used as classroom activities to engage the students in a more productive way.

In the Role-play learners would be given different roles and they would be spontaneously acting out of situations, without costumes or scripts. For the given context for the role-play, roles are selected. Everything should happen extempore. In a role play session when the student is given a particular role to play out (a particular character to present) will need "imagination" to be able to get "into" the role. At the conclusion, students often discuss about their feeling over the situation and their knowledge acquirement in it.

In both role-play and simulation, the learners assume roles and act, but they are different from each other. Simulations often explore the core themes, issues, in integrated manner. In fact, simulations may be held as more structured role-plays. In simulations, the students would be provided with some context, to act out real-life situations (like acting as buyers and sellers bargaining and negotiating with

each other to present a market scene). Thus, by simulating the marketplace, they strike deals for the exchange of some commodity the good, and eventually learning the market behavior.

These two devices are very much feasible in the classroom situation that has ample scope for improving the learning environment. Learners are from different background, energetic, enthusiastic, and ready to grab opportunities to act, to showcase their talents, and thereby to learn through new experiences.

As these devices must be very useful in many other spheres of life, like clubs, healthcare system, corporate world, transport, trade and commerce, sports etc. non-teachers also can resort to simulation and role play easily. In fact, these have several advantages:

- They develop creativity and positive attitudes;
- They can help all learn to reflect on and extend knowledge;
- They help all link theory with practice;
- They help learners develop self-confidence among them;
- They help learners in develop social skills like social manners and etiquettes;
- They facilitate learners to get into the position of the other individuals.

6.2 ELT class and ‘Creative Deviation’: Learning through TV / Radio news

An exposure to the English-speaking environment is difficult to have for the students in the rural areas in India. However, in this digital era or in the time of AI, it is not that difficult too. Listening to news bulletin or sport commentary would very good alternative resources to develop the listening and speaking kills. Let’s take up, for example, a news item on TV, and check the probable benefits the whole class may have.

Source: NDTV bulletin, dated 19.01.2021

President Ram Nath Kovind today congratulated the Indian cricket team for scripting a historic triumph in a Test series in Australia, saying the nation is proud of their achievement. India won the fourth and final Test of the series with three wickets, clinching the Border-Gavaskar Trophy by 2-1. “A historic cricketing triumph scripted in Australia! Congratulations to India’s talented young cricket team for winning the hard-fought test series. The team showed exceptional skills and resilience. The nation is proud of their achievement,” Kovind tweeted.

Earlier, Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi also took to the micro-blogging site to praise the team for showing “remarkable energy and passion” throughout the series.

PM Modi said team showed stellar intent, remarkable grit and determination to defeat Australia in their own backyard, despite missing several key players due to injuries.

“We are all overjoyed at the success of the Indian Cricket Team in Australia. Their remarkable energy and passion were visible throughout. So were their stellar intent, remarkable grit and determination. Congratulations to the team! Best wishes for your future endeavours,” tweeted PM Narendra Modi.

From this news and the learners acting as careful listeners should be guided by the teacher who can plan for his lesson in the following way:

In the basic a framework useful in designing a plan for a listening lesson the steps will be:

- Pre-listening (motivation, contextualization, preparation)
- While listening
- Post-listening

- **Pre-listening**

- o Students are to share with all their love for games and sports (motivation),

- Students will be interviewed about their knowledge of cricket and India's performance (contextualization),
- Students who listen to cricket news and match commentaries would share their listening experiences (contextualization),
- Students will remember the great Indian achievements on the cricket field (preparation).

- **While listening**

- Students listen attentively and decide whether it is a good news or bad for them as cricket lovers.
- Can mark the individualities of different persons' reaction to the great Indian victory and their uses of English—of Modi, of our President and that of the script-writer.
- Students listen and will be recording/processing information in their brain/memory.

- **Post-listening**

- Having the content
 - ◆ Discuss what they feel about this achievement of India
 - ◆ Can discuss similar other achievements, can make some comparisons
 - ◆ Can discuss the role of social media in connecting to everyone instantly
- Learning the form
 - ◆ Students look back at the structure and proportion of the different information provided
 - ◆ Students may find some new words in the news item, and by using the contextual cues must find out what they mean
 - ◆ Students must pay attention to the phrases and the rule of collocations working in the content.

7. Analysis

Coming to the conclusive part of our discussion it can be said, "Effective teaching-learning process needs to be learner-centered but teacher-driven". Both teacher and the students have specific roles to play in an effective process of teaching-learning. Let's first look at how the student-centric approach may be beneficial for the learners. This kind of approach helps the learners to learn through their mistakes and through the modes of fun and enjoyment. They learn to take responsibilities, and thereby must get prepared for many of the possible adulthood distractions. Students can identify better their own interests, individuality, learning styles etc. They can also learn how to collaborate with others, learn from the peers, to manage time and their discretions. Because of deeper involvement, the student-centric approach can imbue into them a greater love for and attachment to the lesson. Active participation can ensure and encourages their faculty of critical thinking, can provide them with a better understanding of the ways of the world, and teaches them social skills. A student-centric class-room is always lively and spontaneous, rather than a quiet and rigid one. However, the whole of the classroom affairs should not be left to the learners only, where the teacher's role will be mar-

ginalized. An effective teaching learning process must be teacher-driven, i.e. regulated and monitored by the teacher. A teacher must be very much on the driver's seat to steer the class and the teaching-learning process in the following ways:

- o By putting thought-provoking questions (during or after the lesson is complete), which would motivate the learners to think on their own, and thereby to turn into more independent;
- o By bringing in technology in the class wherever they might be more beneficial;
- o By providing the students with their practical experiences that would supplement their theoretical knowledge.
- o By giving the students appropriate tasks from time to time.

The teacher must take care of the class, must regulate the direct the students. He must facilitate learning with help, guidance, and by creating a proper learning environment. He would have control over the class and monitor the progress of the students by planning the lessons, conducting frequent assessments, and setting the objectives to be achieved. For some better learning outcome, the teacher must create an effective and democratic environment where every student can participate, face challenges, and find their own solutions to the problems. The teacher should function as a manager in the class rather than a dictator. He should have a better organization of the learning materials, must have a managerial approach toward the learners' activities and the teaching-learning processes in a holistic manner.

8. Conclusion

But beside the heterogeneous factors discussed in the sections above, the learners themselves often have different agenda, thereby making the task of a teacher even more complicated. The best solution on the part of a teacher in this context would be first to identify efficiency-based or background-based groups, and then to deal with them accordingly. The peer teaching or 'heterogeneous grouping' may be effective in many other cases, but special attention to the back-loggers is also a necessity. Paying attention to the learners' receptive skills in language learning (reading and listening), the whole discussion so far has established all the classroom challenges posed potentially by students' heterogeneity and prescriptivism of the curriculum. The prospective measures like 'productive digression', 'creative deviation', remedial classes, exposing students to the English-speaking environments and many others can be adopted in the heterogenous L₂ classrooms, and the teacher can go beyond the prescribed bounds of the syllabus in order to ensure teaching-learning environment as well as some substantial progress in the learners' L₂ acquisition.

9. Word Notes

1. A curriculum is a systematic educational framework for an academic program, but a syllabus is a part of the curriculum, a document detailing the course contents, time frame and outlines about tests and evaluation processes to measure learners' achievements. The curriculum may be prescriptive very often, creating the education trajectory with a broader perspective. On the other hand, the syllabus is generally descriptive in nature, highlighting or specifying the content. However, when the curriculum is prescriptive to a greater degree, the syllabus may also become prescriptive. Then it leaves less scopes for the teachers to be innovative and original. The 'prescribed syllabus' often functions as a binding or obligatory contract, creating a boundary for the mandatory course contents, reading materials,

and assessment methods for a specific course.

2. In a heterogeneous classroom learners have varying in (i) social backgrounds, (ii) levels pre-existing academic achievements, and (iii) different language proficiency (oral and written) levels.

3. Language proficiency means a language user’s ability or fluency in using the language in order to communicate well and serve his/her real-world purposes no matter what the topics and settings are. Often held to be synonymous to proficiency, language efficiency actually means achieving competence through consistent target-bound practice, error minimization and maximizing speech rate in communication and fluency in writing.

4. As an educational practice, often adopted in a large classroom, heterogeneous grouping is the one where students who differ in abilities, skills, pre-existing knowledge base or social backgrounds are treated as a single unit and put collectively in the same learning group.

10. Appendix-I

<p>A. Virtue GEORGE HERBERT</p> <p>Sweet day, so cool, so calm, so bright, The bridal of the earth and sky; The dew shall weep thy fall to-night, For thou must die.</p> <p>Sweet rose, whose hue angry and brave Bids the rash gazer wipe his eye; Thy root is ever in its grave, And thou must die.</p> <p>Sweet spring, full of sweet days and roses, A box where sweets compacted lie; My music shows ye have your closes, And all must die.</p> <p>Only a sweet and virtuous soul, Like season’d timber, never gives; But though the whole world turn to coal, Then chiefly lives.</p>	<p>B. The Song of the Whale KIT WRIGHT</p> <p>Heaving mountain in the sea, Whale, I heard you Grieving. Great whale crying for your life, Crying for your kind, I knew How we would use Your dying: Lipstick for our painted faces, Polish for our shoes. Tumbling mountain in the sea, Whale I heard you Calling. Bird-high notes, kenning, soaring: At their edge a tiny drum Like a heartbeat. We would make you Dumb. In the forest of the sea, Whale I heard you Singing, Singing to your kind. We’ll never let you be. Instead of life we choose Lipstick for our painted faces, Polish for our shoes.</p>
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